

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE MANIFESTATION OF REFLEXIVITY DURING STUDENT LIFE

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Annotation. The article presents the content of the concept of reflection, an analysis of the scientific research of foreign psychologists in the framework of the problem. According to him, an analysis of the theoretical approaches advanced to the concept of reflection is described. In particular, the results of an experimental study of the degree of formation of refraction during student life are presented.

Keywords: reflection, self-observation, personality, activity, behavior, self-control, self-control, self-control, self-attitude, self-accounting, self-understanding, self-knowledge.

Аннотация. В статье представлено содержание понятия рефлексии, проведен анализ научных исследований зарубежных психологов в рамках рассматриваемой проблемы. По его словам, описан анализ теоретических подходов, выдвинутых к понятию рефлексии. В частности, представлены результаты экспериментального исследования степени сформированности рефракции в течение студенческой жизни.

Ключевые слова: рефлексия, самонаблюдение, личность, деятельность, поведение, самоконтроль, саморегуляция, самообладание, самоотношение, самоотчетность, самопонимание, самопознание.

Аннотация. Мақолада рефлексия тушунчасининг мазмуни, хориж психологларнинг муаммо доирасидаги илмий изланишларининг таҳлиллари келтирилган. Унга кўра, рефлексия тушунчасига нисбатан илгари сурилган назарий ёндашувларнинг таҳлиллари баён қилинган. Айниқса, талабалик даврида рефлексияни шаклланганлик даражасини экспериментал ўрганиш натижалари келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: рефлексия, ўзини ўзи кузатиш, шахс, фаолият, хулқ-атвор, ўзини ўзи назорат қилиш, ўзини ўзи бошқариш, ўзига бўлган муносабат, ўз-ўзига ҳисоб бериш, ўзини ўзи тушуниш, ўзини ўзи билиш.

Reflection is the ability to understand personal characteristics, how they are perceived by those around them, as well as to shape their own Hulk, taking into account the reactions to be expected.

In the encyclopedic dictionary of pedagogy, reflection is interpreted in a different way. Reflection - (from the Latin reflexio - look back) - reflection, self-observation. In philosophy – a form of human theoretical activity aimed at reflection on personal behavior and their laws. The desire to understand one's own actions and feelings and their laws, to learn from the mysteries of the universe is being identified early on; at all stages of Culture, a person began to think about the motives of his actions. Nevertheless, most of these behaviors do not have conscious motives. It is for this reason that secondary explanations are sought for simple behavior that do not belong to their historical origin, but reflect conclusions based on the general knowledge of the people in question. The existence of such secondary annotations is considered one of the main anthropological phenomena. At the same time, most human beings initially commit behaviors, and then try to justify them. In the psychological dictionary, the concept of reflection is explained as follows: reflection (lot. reflexio-hindsight) is the process of perception of internal psychic acts and states by a subect. There are many approaches to the problem of reflection in the scientific literature. In modern encyclopedias, reflection is indicated as a mental process that is directed towards self-awareness, understanding, analysis in general-its behavior, behavior, speech, experience, emotions, States, character, attitude towards oneself and others, tasks, tasks.

According to J. Locke, reflection is an observation that engages the mind's activity. In a short psychological dictionary, the concept of reflection is explained as follows: reflection (lat. reflexio - look back, reference) is the process of self-awareness of internal mental acts and situations by the subject. The concept of reflection arose in the science of philosophy, and it means the process of thinking about what is happening in the mind of an individual.

R. Descartes coordinated reflection with the individual's ability to distance himself from all external, physical things and focus on the content of his thoughts. Dj. Locke distinguished intuition and reflection, and interpreted reflection as a separate source of knowledge (an internal experience that differs from the external one based on the senses). In these views, a person's ability to self-report on the phenomena of consciousness experienced by him, to analyze his personal mental state has changed inadequately. Reflection is looking back, that is, the ability of a person to refer to the

initial state of his thoughts, actions and actions several times, to be able to stand in the place of an external observer, to know what he is doing, how he perceives, including how he perceives himself. But it is not only the subject's self-understanding and knowledge, but also determining how others know and understand him, his personal characteristics, emotional reactions, and cognitive (cognitive) perceptions. A special form of reflection - subject-reflexive relations develops when the subject of cooperation is manifested as the essence of these imaginations.

Reflection as a mechanism is formed somewhat later than identification. If the ability to identify is manifested in a child very early, the first signs of reflection develop in a preschool child, and as a source of acquisition of new knowledge, it develops in students of junior school age. Reflection helps to withdraw, to occupy different situations, which, in turn, allows for a deep and complete analysis of oneself.

Reflection is not only a process of self-understanding, self-awareness. It includes the processes of understanding and evaluating others. With the help of reflection, the coordination of one's consciousness, values, thoughts related to values with the surrounding people, groups, society, and finally, universal thoughts and relations is realized. To analyze something is to experience, to pass through one's inner world, to evaluate. Each person's world of reflection is individual, diverse and rich in content. It is the ability to reflect that allows a person to form actions, the meaning of life and imagination, and to eliminate those that are of a low level of effectiveness. An important aspect of reflection is the ability to manage personal activity in accordance with personal values and thoughts, to form new mechanisms in connection with the changed tasks, goals and conditions of activity and to switch to them. Reflection serves to think about the past and see the future. The commonality of all tariffs is that reflection is the ability of a person to describe himself from the outside, analyze his actions, and change them if necessary [2].

Students are young people who are preparing for production activities. Educating students is influencing their psyche and activity in order to form personality traits and characteristics such as ability, awareness, sense of duty, discipline, working with people, self-criticism.

The student period consists of the second stage of adolescence, includes 17-22-25 years and is characterized by a number of unique features and contradictions. Therefore, the period of adolescence begins with the realization of a person's social and professional status. During this period, adolescents experience a kind of mental

crisis - or stress, they try to quickly fulfill the roles of adults in various forms /whether they like it or not, according to new aspects of lifestyle. marriage begins. The transition process of the lifestyle of adults causes internal contradictions depending on the characteristics of a person's maturation.

Students are taught to learn independently, organize their own activities, manage SELF, develop new ideas, etc. The main factor for the implementation of these tasks is the transition from a monologic lecture to a dialogical lecture based on the dialogue between the student and the teacher.

Psychologists B.G. Ananov, N.V. Kuzmina, N.F. Talzina, V.Y. Lyaudis, I.S. Cohn, V.T. Lisovsky, A.A. Bodalev, A.V. Petrovsky, M.G. Davletshin, I.I. Ilyasov, A.V. Dmitrieva, Z.F. Yesareva, AA. Verbisk, VA. According to the studies of Tokareva, E.G.Ghozieva, R.Z.Gainuddinov and others, it is difficult for students to get an education in higher educational institutions, because during this period, the complex qualities and qualities of a person improve.

One of the characteristics of social and psychological growth at this age is the increase in motivation to study. Although the growth of moral processes in students is slow, but the most important qualities of character - independence, initiative, resourcefulness, insight, etc. are improving. Also, they are increasingly interested in social situations, reality, and moral rules, and their desire to implement them.

In the student years, the process of self-improvement plays an important role in the life and activities of young people, but the components of study management (self-monitoring, analysis, evaluation and verification, etc.) is of particular importance. By comparing the ideal /high, stable, perfect/ "me" with the real /concrete event/ "me", the components of self-management will have a practical expression. From the point of view of the student, the ideal "I" has not been sufficiently checked based on a certain criterion, so it is inevitable that they feel random and unnatural, therefore, the real "I" is also far from the true assessment of his personality, such an obstacle in the improvement of the student's personality positive contradictions create internal insecurity in relation to one's personality and a negative attitude towards studying.

The second period of adolescence is distinguished by features of demandingness and determination beyond the ability to assess behavior and reality. Therefore, students cannot always be principled. Some assertiveness

also translates into a negative attitude toward adults. Students' rejection of the teacher's recommendations often causes conflicts.

Knowing the structure and nature of this or that trait, it is possible to use the educational opportunities of various subjects: to cultivate interest in the chosen profession and to like the chosen profession in higher school - to correctly imagine the social importance of the chosen profession in students, about the suitability of each student for his profession firm confidence, understanding the need to master all the subjects provided for in the curriculum of a higher educational institution, the way to self-educate for the benefit of work, to constantly supplement one's knowledge is carried out with [3].

It is known that the study of the factors affecting the formation of reflection during the student period shows how important the problem is. For this purpose, experimental work was organized using the method of determining the level of reflection of the test subjects. The data obtained from the results of the research were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality.

Table 1

Levels of manifestation of reflection during the student period

Sinaluvchi	Retrospective reflection of activity	Reflection of current (existing, current) activity	Review of future activities	Communication and reflection of interaction with other people
1st course	14,8%	26,2%	29,4%	29,6%
3rd course	15,3%	28,3%	31%	25,4%

If we analyze the results collected by the testers according to the methodology, significant differences can be seen between them. Especially if at first it was difficult for them to organize their activities, and later, they were enriched with the increase of skills and knowledge.

We can see that the indicators of the requirements of the 3rd course have increased in a certain sense. Because it can be explained by the fact that they have increased life experience, skills and knowledge. The main thing is that they actively analyze the surrounding events and have a strong independent approach.

If we analyze the results according to the next scale of the methodology, it is (26.2% and 28.3%) in the group of testers. It is distinguished by the stability of their aspirations in relation to the type of activity they have chosen at the moment. Also, according to the indicators of the testers, it was found that the reflection of current (existing, current) activity is significant in the group of 3rd year students. If this is the strength of their need to continue their chosen type of activity in the future, the 1st year students state that their current activities are not stable and may change due to the circumstances.

In the test group, it was found that the indicators of the 3rd year students differed significantly on the scale of consideration of future activities. According to him, the indicators are 29.4% and 31%, which indicates that their visions about the future have been realized, albeit a little. It is important not to forget that there is a complex psychological phenomenon in front of them, such as choosing a profession and becoming a specialist.

The main task of communication during the student period is to determine and master the elementary norms of friendship and companionship. The main feature of student communication is that it is subject to a complete code of friendship. The character of students' communication with their parents and adults is formed on the basis of their sense of adulthood. They are deeply concerned about the resistance and objections expressed by adults to restricting the rights of students. They need the support of adults in communication.

Joint activities help students to better understand adults. The student feels a great need to share with adults about the changes that are taking place in him, the problems that concern him, but he is never the first to start it. The student strongly complains about being treated like a young child, student communication is characterized by extreme volatility. Imitation of someone's behavior is characteristic of the student period. Often, they imitate the actions of adults they know and like.

In the psychology of creativity, communication is studied as the interaction of people with each other and in the process of mutual action. Communication between people is a necessary condition for human existence. People behave differently when they are alone. They behave differently when communicating with other people. V.M. Bekhterov emphasized that the influence of the group on the individual is permanent. Exclamation (a person's energy increases in the presence of other people). There are types such as activator (trying not to fall behind the

members of the group in the process of human activity) or loser (inhibiting the demonstration of the individuality of the group's individual activity).

In the studies of V.M. Bekhterev, M.V. Lange, V.E. Myasishev, F. Allport, V. Myode, A. Mito, D. Mareno and others, it has been proven that it has a great influence on the mental activity of a person, work ability, interpersonal communication, and the cooperative activities of people. It will be more productive to analyze the results of personal activity in the team, to compare them with the results of the activities of their comrades. According to F.D. Gorbov's researches, under certain circumstances, working together as a team allows each member of the group to develop a personality. This joint activity occurs in cohesive groups [1].

It is known that the reflection of communication and interaction with other people during the student period is 29.6% and 25.4%. If we look at the results of the methodology, most of the time of the 1st year students is spent on the streets, among peers and adults. Therefore, we can see that this scale is strong in the group of 1st year students. It shows that the main goal of our 3rd year students is to strive to become a qualified specialist in the future, to acquire the ability to deal with pressure and analytical approach in any situation.

Based on the above, it is possible to make the following conclusions, that is, the increase in self-knowledge of the student can affect the formation of reflection. The existence of a desire for self-knowledge, in particular, serves to form a unique system of views regarding their activities, the future, and the process of communication. Even if this is the case, it indicates that they have developed self-awareness, control, management, and education depending on their age.

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